

Data skills for agroecologists

Aboubacari Abdou Amadou, [Lily Clements](#), Lucie Hazelgrove Planel and David Stern
IDEMS International
lucie@idems.international

This paper presents a training model developed by IDEMS to support researchers in agroecology across West Africa (Mali, Niger, and Burkina Faso) in the statistical analysis of data from agricultural experiments and surveys. As our training courses are for non-statisticians, our approach prioritises accessibility and contextual relevance. We illustrate this approach through a six-day introductory course delivered in early 2025 for NGO staff with university-level education but limited formal training in mathematics or statistics. Grounded in five guiding values: modular open educational resources, local facilitation, software-agnostic methods, the use of participants' institutional data, and an analysis-first approach, the model offers a scalable and adaptable approach to statistical education in applied, real-world contexts.

INTRODUCTION

Despite decades of reform in statistics education, most teaching still falls short of the ideals proposed in the literature. Calls to centre learning on real data, to prioritise understanding over software commands, and to reduce mathematical prerequisites remain more aspirational than widespread practice. In many contexts - particularly in low-resource or applied settings - statistics is still taught as a sequence of formulas or software steps, detached from the messy, context-rich nature of real-world data.

This is not due to a lack of guidance. Cobb (2015) argued that statistics instruction should begin with data, not methods. The GAISE College Report (Carver et al., 2016) reinforced the importance of active, concept-driven learning using real-world data. Wickham (2014) and others have stressed the centrality of data wrangling and cleaning as a core part of the data analysis process – not a preliminary step to be glossed over. Curriculum innovations such as those in New Zealand (Forbes 2013; Arnold, Trinick and Pfannkuch 2022) have shown the value of students working with their own data and real questions. Yet these insights remain under-implemented, especially in professional and applied training contexts.

Structural barriers compound the issue. Especially in low-resource environments, commercial software, coding-intensive tools, and pre-packaged examples alienate learners who lack time, equipment, or prior exposure. International experts lack the cultural experience to contextualise learning materials and adapt their teaching to local learners' needs. Models such as the LISA 2020 initiative (Vance et al., 2022) demonstrate how empowering local facilitators to support applied statistics can build capacity and contextual relevance, but scaling such efforts remains a challenge.

At IDEMS, we believe it is not only possible but essential to reframe statistical education. As a result, we have developed a flexible, modular approach rooted in five core concepts that align with the realities and needs of learners in applied, low-resource settings:

1. Adaptable, open educational resources. Modular teaching materials, including guides and STACK-based quizzes, that can be reused, translated, and tailored to local needs.

2. Training through local facilitation. An apprenticeship model to enable local facilitators to take ownership of the course ensures sustainability and contextual grounding.

3. Software-agnostic. Encouraging the use of tools users are confident with, with additional support offered for accessible software like R-Instat creates an inclusive learning environment.

4. Use both cleaned and raw datasets. Incorporating a range of datasets, including cleaned and raw versions of the same data, to support a range of learning outcomes.

5. A context driven learning approach. Prioritising use of an institution's datasets enables student-led learning which both reduces barriers and increases the relevance of the course.

These values are rooted in evidence from statistics education, but also reflect what we have found to work in practice. This paper is structured around these five values and presents a case study of their implementation in a six-day training course in Mali in early 2025. The course was designed for NGO staff who regularly collect agricultural data but have had limited statistical training. The intention was to bridge the gap between what research recommends and what learners typically experience.

BACKGROUND

A key challenge to development in Africa is the widespread gap in statistical capacity to analyse the increasing volumes of data emerging across sectors, from agriculture to health, education, and development. Despite the increasing availability of data, the tools and training needed to analyse that data have mainly remained inaccessible, overly technical, and/or disconnected from the realities of those expected to use them (Stern, 2017). In response to these challenges, the African Data Initiative (ADI) was created in 2015 to support more practical, inclusive, and context-appropriate approaches to data analysis and statistical development.

A key outcome of ADI was the development of R-Instat, a free and open-source graphical user interface for R, designed to support statistical teaching and learning in low-resource contexts (Parsons et al., 2019). R-Instat was created to reduce barriers for learners and practitioners who needed robust statistical tools without the complexity of programming environments like RStudio. Its emphasis on usability, offline access, and educational workflows makes it especially well-suited to African settings where computing infrastructure and internet connectivity can be limited.

Building on this foundation, our Research Methods team, working in close collaboration with ADI, has been developing regionally grounded approaches to statistical training. We support researchers, NGOs, and educational institutions across the Sahel, particularly through our work with the Collaboration for Resilient Food Systems (CRFS) community of practice, funded by the McKnight Foundation. This community includes nearly 30 research projects in Mali, Niger, and Burkina Faso, many of which conduct participatory research using Farmer Research Network models (Richardson et al, 2021).

Despite growing demand for data-informed decision-making, statistical training in much of the region remains tool-focused. In academic and professional training settings, training often prioritises teaching software commands over interpreting data. Datasets are usually pre-cleaned and generic, with little connection to learners' own work or environments.

These limitations are exacerbated by structural challenges. Many learners in the region have limited access to personal computers, and have less opportunity to gain programming experience. While mobile literacy is high, digital confidence with statistical tools remains low. In practice, learners often memorise sequences of clicks or code, without being supported to ask questions of the data or think critically about what they find.

Our work across the CRFS community has found a growing interest from local organisations and institutions to develop more context-relevant, applied approaches to statistics – ones that build on real data, local questions, and accessible tools. Developing open resources in-region can enable more educators to improve their statistical teaching (Ibanez, Schroeder and Hanwell, 2018).

In early 2025, a Malian NGO requested support to train its staff in basic data analysis skills. The NGO, like many of our partners in the region, operates across ecology, economics, and social development, and regularly collects substantial amounts of field and survey data. There were 19 staff at the workshop, many of whom regularly collected data but had limited training in statistical analysis. While most were university educated, including 11 at Master's level, their professional roles were diverse: from social development leads to geomaticians.

In response, our regional team adapted an existing open course, Introduction to Working with Data, into a six-day training tailored to the organisation's datasets and staff experience levels.

The next section outlines how the course was designed and implemented, and how it fits into broader efforts to rethink statistical training in applied development contexts across West Africa.

METHODS

This section outlines the practical design and delivery of the six-day training course. The course was structured around our five values, each grounded in educational research and developed through experience working in low-resource settings. It concludes with our course evaluation methods.

Adapting Open Resources to Local Needs

We designed the course using open, modular resources developed for previous initiatives, including Pro-RUWA, a regional program focused on research capacity for sustainable agriculture (Pro-

RUWA, n.d.). This component-based format ensures that course content can be rapidly tailored to new audiences and contexts while maintaining a consistent pedagogical foundation.

For this course, most of the training materials were taken from a previous course titled Introduction to Working with Data. This course includes structured guides, practical activities, and interactive quizzes (Clements 2025) developed using the STACK assessment system. STACK enables dynamic, data-driven questions with immediate, personalised feedback and mastery-based progression (Sangwin et al., 2006).

Preparatory discussions with leaders in the NGO allowed the team to identify the NGO's needs to adapt our existing resources into a new, tailored and relevant program. This resulted in a slower paced introductory course, covering key concepts and prioritising the NGOs own work as case studies.

Apprenticeship Model for Local Facilitation

The course was delivered entirely by facilitators from Mali and Niger, all trained using the same open-access modular resources. IDEMS is committed to building sustainable, regionally led teams and has developed a three-stage apprenticeship model in West Africa. This model begins with an open internship, designed to identify promising candidates for apprenticeship, which may in turn lead to a junior fellowship. Participants gradually progress from being learners to facilitators, using the very course resources that trained them. This cyclical model not only reinforces their mastery but also ensures a sustainable, locally led training ecosystem.

Throughout our internship-apprentice-junior fellow program, team members contribute to the ongoing development of our course materials, shaping examples and guides based on their insights and understanding of the local training environment. Their observations and experiences help identify parts of the course needing improvement, enabling a continuous learning cycle for future iterations.

Software Agnostic

Our courses are designed to be software-agnostic, with resources suitable for any environment where spreadsheets or statistical tools are available. The emphasis is on developing the core skills needed to understand, analyse, and interpret data—abilities that transcend any single platform. Participants are free to use whichever software they prefer or have access to, because our priority is not learning a particular tool, but building the transferable expertise to work effectively with data (Pimentel, Horton and Wilkerson 2022).

We aim to create an inclusive learning environment by accommodating diverse technological contexts, at the individual and regional levels. In West Africa, for instance, not all university students have reliable access to proprietary platforms like Microsoft Office or Google Workspace. By developing guides for alternative spreadsheet software, we increase our course accessibility and reach.

Additionally, software availability can change over time; for example, Genstat Discovery Edition was once widely used in low-resource settings but has since been discontinued (VSNi, 2023). R-Instat, a free and open-source graphical user interface for R, has proven to be a valuable alternative for promoting sound statistical practice in low-resource settings as it was specifically designed for contexts with limited resources and minimal coding capacity (Stern, 2017). Designing software-agnostic resources ensures our courses remain adaptable and sustainable in the face of technological shifts.

Using Cleaned and Raw Datasets

The importance of real and realistic data is paramount. IDEMS' open resources include realistic simulated data and case studies based on real data. For learning, realistic data is able to generate issues experienced in real data at a scale which is pedagogically desirable, whereas the real data case studies often include pre-cleaned datasets to enable them to be appropriate for specific learning objectives. This course replaced the case study components of the original Introduction to Working with Data course, to be based around two datasets that were shared in advance, drawn from the NGO's recent surveys and community fieldwork.

To support an error-based learning approach (Metcalf, 2017), where possible, we use two versions of the same dataset in our training courses: one *roughly* pre-cleaned, one raw. Starting with pre-cleaned data allows students to focus on core statistical concepts, such as summary statistics, without being overwhelmed by the complexities of data preparation. A *roughly* cleaned dataset is important as later in-depth cleaning of the raw dataset by the participants highlights how data cleaning decisions can

influence results. By comparing outcomes from the pre-cleaned and raw datasets, students experience firsthand the need for a thorough and critical cleaning process, learning through the discovery of errors and their impact.

The facilitators' preparation of the preliminary, roughly cleaned version for initial analyses is vital also for identifying specific learning points which participants will require in their regular work.

Context Driven Learning Approach

In line with Cobb's call to 'exploit context' (2015) we prioritise context driven learning. By using an institution's own datasets, we remove one barrier to learning and enhance the training's immediate meaning and purpose. We emphasise the real-world agricultural and farming significance of participants' interpretations to make the process more tangible. This approach is particularly engaging for inexperienced learners, who can quickly gain confidence in working with data.

Grounding the learning experience in the participant's contexts enables participants to guide their own learning process through examining their hypothesis and exploring their research questions. Initial analyses and interpretations of the data give direction to the remaining course modules and help students understand the full analytical process. This learner led and context driven model requires flexibility from the facilitators, but the modular course resources and preliminary preparations with the organisation's data provide the structure and confidence to support participants effectively. This practical approach helps learners conceptually understand statistical analysis.

To evaluate the teaching pedagogy and accessibility of our teaching approach, we collected data from four sources. Student data was collected from three sources: 1) daily reflective diaries completed by participants, 2) course quiz results, and 3) online feedback evaluation questionnaires completed at the end of the course. These questionnaires asked two open-ended questions: one to identify learnings, and one to identify challenges - whether at the personal or course level. To complement these data, course facilitators took note of their observations during the six-day program. These observations were vital as participants often focus on their successes. Facilitator observations helped provide context to the challenges participants had during our deductive analysis.

RESULTS

This section presents reflections on how the five design approaches were experienced in practice by participants and facilitators. All quotes have been translated from the original French.

Adapting Open Resources to Local Needs

The modular course resources meant our team could efficiently design a course to suit the NGO's needs. We used the Introduction to Working with Data course materials as a basis, and created new materials following the NGO's need for basic introductory materials. IDEMS is building up a bank of reusable resources that will make course creation an exercise in adaptation, rather than creation.

For course participants, the STACK quizzes in particular were frequently highlighted as an engaging and effective learning tool due to the immediate feedback and the mastery design where users can repeat different versions of the same question. The interactive feedback encouraged autonomy, and participants were able to identify and correct their own misunderstandings. While one participant was pleased that:

"the exercise and the quiz really helped me to assimilate [how to clean data]." Participant's daily reflection.

another participant felt that:

"For future occasions, it would be preferable for the trainer to carry out the analyses by projecting, and we are going to do this with him in order to move more quickly." Participant survey feedback.

This highlights the unfamiliarity of our learner-led pedagogical approach to some. Facilitators however noted that while some participants initially struggled with the unfamiliar self-guided format, most adapted quickly and appreciated the independence it allowed.

Apprenticeship Model for Local Facilitation

Facilitators played a central role in creating and delivering the course. The West Africa team were familiar with the course tools and materials, having been introduced to them during their internship training, and having already supported the facilitation of other courses with these same materials.

“Our participation in the design of the course ensured we knew the content... we could facilitate the course with ease.” Facilitator reflection.

The West Africa team took the lead in translating existing resources and making small modifications to aid understanding. They created new materials to suit the agricultural data context. The facilitators’ observations of how participants used course resources identified further areas for improvement in the materials, ensuring their continued development.

In delivering the course, facilitators were able to shape the course dynamically in response to participant needs. Because they had previously engaged with the course materials as learners, they were well-positioned to support others in navigating the guides and STACK quizzes. Facilitators knew which STACK mastery quizzes would provide the greatest learning opportunities for the participants, and how to support participants understand the hidden traps within a question. The facilitators’ own experiences enabled them to support others as they themselves had been through the same processes, encountering the same challenges to their thinking.

Software Agnostic

Although the course was designed to be software agnostic, all participants ultimately used Excel and R-Instat for their analyses. They found Excel useful for data cleaning, but were keen to progress from Excel to R-Instat due to the professional graphics it gives access to.

“An interesting discussion emerged on the importance of choosing the right software for each type of analysis.” Participant’s daily reflection.

“Using Excel and R-Instat to carry out these analyses was particularly interesting. In Excel, I learnt how to use statistical functions and pivot tables. With R-Instat, I discovered a more automated and advanced approach to statistical analysis.” Participant’s daily reflection.

Even those with some experience in R found the R-Instat interface more intuitive for this context. Participants valued that it enabled them to apply their learning quickly, without the steep learning curve of coding.

“Learnt how to use powerful data analysis tools such as R-instat, which is fast and increases the efficiency and promptness of data analysis.” Participant survey feedback.

Facilitators reported that having a consistent tool made it easier to support learners while maintaining the flexibility for others to use alternatives where appropriate.

Using Cleaned and Raw Datasets

Starting with a cleaned dataset enabled participants to create engaging visualisations and apply core concepts early in the course, giving them an immediate sense of achievement. Facilitators observed that some participants became demotivated when cleaning raw data later in the week. While essential, data cleaning is often a less engaging entry point for learners. Introducing more immediately rewarding tasks early on noticeably built confidence and motivation, better preparing participants for the more technical challenges later in the course.

Cleaning the organisation’s raw data and comparing it to the roughly pre-cleaned data led to extended discussions about data quality and interpretability. Participants came to see that certain questions could not be answered reliably without revisiting the original data collection process.

While using an organisation’s own data in a course offers clear benefits, it also presents several challenges. For this NGO as with many research institutions, concerns were raised about sharing unpublished data due to issues of data ownership and confidentiality. Course facilitators are now

familiar with this “problem of data ownership”. Even with published data, sharing it within the course can expose the owner(s) to critique or the embarrassment of previously unnoticed errors in analysis or interpretation. In both cases, careful management and clear communication is needed to build the trusting and collaborative learning environment needed.

Context Driven Learning Approach

Working with data collected by their own organisation made the course immediately relevant and meaningful to participants. Facilitators reported that using familiar data simplified the learning process:

“The use of their data was very interesting. If you have to understand it and then clean it... If you still have to try and understand the database too, that's going to take more time. It's good to work with their data because they know it.” Facilitator reflection.

Facilitators found that the course structure, focusing on student-led learning, worked well: participants remained focused and independent, referring to the course materials and facilitators when they wanted support.

“What I appreciated most was the pedagogical approach, which combined theory and practice, making learning more concrete.” Participant’s daily reflection.

Daily reflections, verbal and written, were used to adapt the next day's content, helping trainers respond to questions and identify areas needing further clarification. The practical approach was cited as one of the most valuable aspects of the course, enabling learners to quickly see how the techniques applied to their day-to-day work.

IMPLICATIONS

This training is part of a growing framework for how statistical education can be locally adapted, globally connected, and openly shared. Through this work, we are developing a modular approach that allows courses to be tailored to the needs of specific institutions, while still drawing from a shared bank of open educational resources. These materials, including guides, simulated and real-world data, and STACK-based quizzes, can be flexibly adapted and recontextualised across settings, building toward an interoperable global framework for foundational data training.

The goal is not uniformity, but adaptability. By building strong, openly available resources and pairing them with contextualised delivery through local facilitators, we believe it is possible to create sustainable and scalable training ecosystems. This work contributes to an evolving ecosystem already seeded through ADI, and the invitation now is to make it broader. These tools and models need not remain regional. The frameworks developed here offer a potential model for international collaboration, where global tools are combined with locally-led implementation.

The IDEMS apprenticeship model shows one pathway toward building the facilitation capacity needed to make this vision real. While we expect our framework to be applicable across different contexts, we believe the training and support of facilitators is the area most in need of contextual adaptation. Future scaling will depend not just on resources, but on how they are interpreted, adapted, and delivered by people who understand the contexts they serve.

CONCLUSION

It’s been nearly a decade since the launch of ADI, and many of the barriers it identified, from inaccessible software to disconnected pedagogy, are being actively removed. We are now entering a new phase, where regional teams are not only using open tools like R-Instat, but also building and delivering high-quality training rooted in local institutions, languages, and data.

This course marks a point of convergence: we believe that our open resources, local facilitation models and pedagogical approaches can provide a model for others in the teaching of statistics. While ADI began in Kenya, it has since spread across the continent and these initiatives are taking root in small but growing pockets. While they are firmly grounded in African contexts, the ideas, tools, and pedagogical models developed through ADI have relevance far beyond the continent. This is an exciting

moment to present this work to an international audience. The hope and expectation is that these resources, including open courses, STACK quizzes, and tools like R-Instat, are now mature enough to have global impact. The next step is collaboration: input from international partners will be key to refining, scaling, and embedding these approaches in diverse contexts around the world.

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